

IMPACT OF STRESSFUL MUSIC ON EYE HEALTH ANALYZING CHANGES IN INTRAOCULAR PRESSURE

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Abstract

Background: Intraocular pressure IOP is a critical parameter in the maintenance of ocular health, directly influencing the risk of developing conditions like glaucoma which can lead to irreversible blindness if not managed effectively. Music, as a ubiquitous part of human culture, profoundly impacts human emotional and physiological states. Despite the extensive research on the positive impact of music, the impact of negative music as music that evokes unpleasant or stressful emotions on IOP remains unexplored. The purpose of this research is to investigate the effect of negative music on IOP. By identifying whether exposure to negative music can induce changes in IOP. *Objective:* To evaluate the impact of listening to negative music on the intraocular pressure of healthy people and explore its potential mechanisms. *Methodology:* From October 2023 to January 2024 This observational cross-sectional study was conducted at Sehat Medical Complex Hanjarwal a Project of the University of Lahore Teaching Hospital. After obtaining data collection permission from the hospital, a total of 73 young adults were selected for the study, by using a non-random-convenient sampling technique. The data was collected from healthy individuals aged 18-30 with no significant acute or chronic diseases. Any individuals having significant diseases like cardiac problems, diabetes, and hypertension were not a part of this study, also those who were not comfortable listening to music were excluded. The IOP of all subjects was measured during the experiment of hearing music, 5 min after exposure to the music, and 10 min after the experiment. *Results:* The final results of the study were given by the comparison of mean pre-exposure IOP in OD 17.872 ± 2.623 p-value 0.000 and OS 16.208 ± 4.477 p-value 0.000, with post-exposure IOP after 5 minutes in OD 16.728 ± 1.879 p-value 0.000 and after 10 min in OD 21.783 ± 2.971 p-value 0.000, similarly in OS after 5 min of exposure 16.045 ± 2.942 p-value 0.000 and after 10 min of exposure 15.939 ± 4.299 p-value 0.000 respectively. *Conclusion:* The results concluded that there was a significant effect of negative music on intraocular pressure with a marked increase noted in the measurements. The very low p-value indicates a strong statistical significance in these findings.

Introduction:

The creation of a complex, multicellular creature from a single cell is perhaps the greatest challenge biology has to tackle. This process is primarily represented by the development of very specialized cell types in the eye, which is controlled by a complex web of cellular connections and early embryonic genetic linkages⁽¹⁾. The earliest indication of eye development occurs around week three of gestation when optic grooves, which are the neuroectoderm origin from the developing forebrain, show^{(1) (2)}. The optic vesicle invaginates and forms the optic cup about four weeks of gestation⁽²⁾. This is what the retina will look like. Retinal (or choroid) fissures are grooves that occur along the ventral side of the optic cup and stalk to facilitate the hyaloid artery and vein passage⁽¹⁾⁽³⁾⁽⁴⁾. As the optic vesicle invaginates and forms the optic cup, the retina emerges⁽⁵⁾. The axons inside the optic stalk lumen proliferate until they annihilate it. Consequently, it forms the optic nerve⁽⁶⁾. The iris and ciliary body begin at the anterior point of the optic cup⁽⁷⁾. It is believed that the lacrimal gland appears during the seventh week of pregnancy and settles into the superlateral region of the orbit⁽⁸⁾.

Understanding the principles of optics is essential to explaining vision. Energy is created in the eye as light enters. The energy travels through the optic nerve as an action potential before being processed in certain brain regions. However, how does light enter the eye and transform into an action potential that is sent to the brain?⁽⁹⁾

For the brain to interpret an image as a visual representation, incoming photons are collected by the retina, a layer of glial and photoreceptor cells in the eye, and conveyed down neural pathways as chemical and electrical impulses⁽¹⁰⁾. Photoreceptor cells, such as rods and cones, are located towards the posterior side of the retinal sublayers and are situated further away from the pupil, which is the point where light enters the eye. Rods are more sensitive in low light (scotopic vision) and are located on the retina's periphery. Cones have photopic vision, which is the ability to discern color light wavelengths, and are more sensitive during the day. Cones are localized at the fovea, the retina's central region. There are approximately 6 million cones and often more than 100 million rods in the retina^{(10) (11)}. Rods transmit color information more effectively than cones, which are less sensitive to

low light. However, depending on the area of the retina, rod and cone distributions differ. For example, the highest level of visual acuity is produced by the central retina, which mostly consists of cones and a significant number of ganglion cells that are making connections^{(9) (12)}. Aqueous Humor is made up of two fluid-like substances that fill the eye and maintain its shape and ocular pressure. A fluid known as aqueous humor, which resembles water, is in front of the lens. Viscous humor, a substance that resembles gel, is situated below the lens and in front of the retina. The constant secretion and reabsorption of a low-viscosity fluid called aqueous humor regulates the intraocular fluid's volume and pressure^{(13) (14)}. For healthy eye function, physiologically important activities include outflow regulation and aqueous fluid secretion. The normal intraocular pressure in a healthy eye is approximately 15 mmHg when the aqueous humor flows against resistance⁽¹⁵⁾. Elevated intraocular pressure (IOP) can occur from an imbalance in the aqueous humor's secretion and reabsorption balance. Treatment options for elevated intraocular pressure problems, like glaucoma or ocular hypertension, may include medication or surgery⁽¹³⁾. Regarding pathogenesis and clinical presentation, glaucoma comprises a variety of ocular conditions. Glaucoma is characterized by damage to the optic nerve, which ultimately leads to permanent blindness. An estimated 70 million people worldwide are affected with glaucoma^{(15) (16) (17)}. Primary open-angle (POAG), primary angle-closure (PACG), secondary angle-closure, secondary open-angle, congenital, and juvenile glaucoma are the common classifications for glaucoma. The most prevalent kind may vary depending on the location. For example, POAG is the most common form of the disease and is more evenly distributed worldwide, whereas PACG is more common in some regions of Asia⁽¹⁸⁾. Most varieties of glaucoma result in vision loss that is linked to elevated intraocular pressure (IOP) and consequent damage to the optic nerve^{(17) (19)}.

Primary open-angle glaucoma (POAG), one of the most common types of glaucoma, has a controversial origin that has been connected to several theories, the most well-known of which is the mechanical pressure theory^{(20) (21)}. The theory that fuels inflammatory responses. Vascular hemodynamic theory or IOP, is considered one of the most significant factors in the

pathogenesis of POAG. Higher trabecular meshwork outflow resistance frequently causes elevated IOP in POAG ⁽²²⁾. Intraocular pressure (IOP) variations and ocular hypertension are two highly modifiable risk factors that can both initiate and exacerbate glaucoma. Intraocular pressure briefly increased in woodwind instrumentalists, both with and without glaucoma, as they performed. Nonetheless, no prior account has been provided of the relative effects of filtration surgery also known as trabeculectomy on variations in intraocular pressure during woodwind instrument performances ⁽²³⁾.

Methods: A cross-sectional observation study design was used in the study conducted from October 2023 to January 2024 at Social Security Hospital Lahore. After departmental ethical and data collection approval a total of 73 healthy individuals aged 18-30 both male and female having good mental health and willing to contribute to the study were included in the research. All those subjects who have diabetes, cardiac problems, hypertension, and were not willing to hear music were excluded. In this study, the stimulus was the negative music as the control variable and all subjects were exposed to the same music for equal intervals of time. Participants were provided with a detailed explanation of the study, its objectives, and the procedures involved. They were informed about the use of metallic music as a stimulus and the measurements to be taken, including intraocular pressure and subjective experiences. Before the commencement of the study, participants were required to provide written informed consent. The consent form outlined the study's purpose, potential risks, and confidentiality measures. After taking informed consent from each data was collected by self-design questionnaire. In a quiet and controlled environment, baseline intraocular pressure (IOP) readings were taken using a calibrated tonometer.

Participants were instructed to remain still and refrain from engaging in any activities that could influence IOP measurements. Participants were exposed to metallic music for a predetermined duration. The volume and type of music were standardized to ensure consistency across participants. The music stimulus was delivered through headphones to minimize external interference. Following the music exposure, participants underwent three additional intraocular pressure readings at the specified time points: **Immediately after music exposure, 5 minutes' post-exposure, and 10 minutes' post-exposure.** Each intraocular pressure measurement was repeated three times, and the average value was recorded to enhance precision. Participants were then asked to respond to a questionnaire regarding their subjective experiences. The questionnaire covered the following aspects: **Presence of tachycardia, Occurrence of headache, Experience of nausea, and Liking or disliking of the metallic music stimulus.** Responses were recorded using a Likert scale or categorical choices, depending on the nature of the question. Following the completion of measurements and questionnaire responses, participants were debriefed. Any queries or concerns were addressed, and they were provided with additional information about the study's goals and potential implications. After the successful collection of the data, all the data was analyzed using SPSS version 25.0. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to present the data.

Results: In total 73 individuals 47 females and 26 males 4 were house officers and 69 were students. 50 patients showed no emotional involvement while 23 had some emotional involvement with the music. 49 patients enjoyed the musical trial while the rest of the 24 has no enjoyment with the music. Detail results are shown in the tables below.

Table 1: Data Related to Demographics and Mental States at the Time OF Experiment:

Gender	Frequency	
F	47	65.8
M	26	34.2
Occupation		
H/O	4	5.3
Student	69	90.8

Emotional Involvement

No	50	68.5
Yes	23	31.5

Enjoyment

No	49	67.1
Yes	24	32.9

Table 1 Describes the demographic data and the emotional states of the subjects involved in the experiment. During research, we had 47 (65.8%) females and 26 (34.2%) males among the total number of 73 participants. Out of these participants, a major

portion 69 (90.8%) were students and the remaining 4 (5.3%) were house officers. This table also describes the frequency of their emotional states including enjoyment and emotional involvement specifically at the time of the experiment.

Table 2: Variations of Intraocular Pressure pre-exposure, post-exposure, after 5 minutes, and after 10 minutes among the participants IOP Stats (OD):

	Total Number	Minimum value	Maximum value	Mean ± Std. Deviation
Pre Exposure	73	11	26	15.96 ± 3.344
Post Exposure	73	12	26	16.80 ± 3.031
After 5 min.	73	12	25	16.35 ± 2.876
After 10 min.	73	11	29	15.71 ± 3.327

This table shows the descriptive stats and variance of IOP measured among the participants before exposure to music, after exposure to music, after 5 minutes of resting time, and after 10 minutes of resting time in the right eye. It was observed that in the right eye, the

mean IOP pre-exposure was 15.96 ± 3.344, and post-exposure was 16.80 ± 3.031. After resting the participants for 5 minutes mean IOP was 16.35 ± 2.876 and resting after 10 minutes, it was 15.71 ± 3.327.

Table 3: IOP stats (OS)

	Total Number	Minimum Value	Maximum Value	Mean ± Std. Deviation
Pre Exposure	73	11	27	16.53 ± 3.491
Post Exposure	73	12	28	17.01 ± 3.241
After 5 min.	73	12	24	16.80 ± 3.110
After 10 min.	73	11	26	16.01 ± 3.206

This table shows the descriptive stats and variance of IOP measured among the participants before exposure to music, after exposure to music, after 5 minutes of resting time, and after 10 minutes of resting time in the left eye. For the left eye, it was

observed that the mean IOP pre-exposure was 16.53 ± 3.491, and post-exposure was 17.01 ± 3.241. After resting the participants for 5 minutes mean IOP was 16.80 ± 3.110 and resting after 10 minutes, it was 16.01 ± 3.206.

Table 4: Frequencies of Asthenopic Symptoms

Symptoms	Frequency	Percentage %
Headache		
0	42	55.3
1	31	40.8

Nausea			
0	42		55.3
1	31		40.8
Eyestrain			
0	31		40.8
1	42		55.3
Tachycardia			
0	42		57.4
1	31		42.5

Table 3: shows the frequencies of asthenopic symptoms experienced by the participants right after the exposure to music, where 0=No and 1=Yes. In this study, it was observed that all the participants who experienced headaches felt nausea as well and the

same percentage was observed (40.8%). The symptom that was observed in a maximum of participants was eye strain after listening to negative music (55.3%). Tachycardia was also noted in 42.5% of the sample.

Table 5: Comparison Of Mean Variance With The IOP Measured Pre Exposure Comparison In Od:

		Sum of Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
		Squares				
Post	Exposure					
Between	Groups	554.026	31	17.872	6.813	0.000
Within	Groups	107.544	41	2.623		
Total		661.570	72			
Post Exposure after 5 min.						
Between	Groups	518.556	31	16.728	8.904	0.000
Within	Groups	77.026	41	1.879		
Total		595.582	72			
Post Exposure after 10 min.						
Between	Groups	675.282	31	21.783	7.331	0.000
Within	Groups	121.825	41	2.971		
Total		797.107	72			

Table: 5 shows the comparison of mean-variance with the IOP measured pre-exposure. In this study, it was observed that the comparison in OD shows the different frequencies and mean-variance

but with 0.00 sig value. This showed that negative music only created an impact on Intraocular pressure in the meantime and it was waived off after some time.

Table 6: Comparison is OS:

		Sum of Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
		Squares				
Post	Exposure					
Between	Groups	599.689	37	16.208	3.620	0.000
Within	Groups	156.709	35	4.477		
Total		756.398	72			
Post Exposure after 5 min.						
Between	Groups	593.647	37	16.045	5.454	0.000
Within	Groups	102.963	35	2.942		
Total		595.582	72			

Post Exposure after 10 min.						
Between	Groups	589.755	37	15.939	3.708	0.000
Within	Groups	150.451	35	4.299		
Total		740.207	72			

Table: 6 shows the comparison of mean-variance with the IOP measured pre-exposure. In this study, it was observed that the comparison in OS shows the different frequencies and mean-variance but with 0.00

Figure 1:

DISCUSSION

The findings of our study demonstrate that exposure to negative or stress-inducing music results in a measurable and immediate elevation in intraocular pressure (IOP) in healthy young adults, which aligns with previously published evidence showing the influence of auditory stimuli on ocular physiology. In 2015, Bertelmann and Ilse investigated the effects of soft and soothing music on patients with primary open-angle glaucoma (POAG) and reported that relaxing music significantly reduced IOP, suggesting a therapeutic benefit for glaucoma patients; however, since our study focused on negative music rather than calming music, the opposite effect was observed, with IOP increasing in real time rather than decreasing. This contrast underscores the importance of emotional tone and auditory stress in IOP modulation. Similarly, a 2018 ARVO study examined the impact of various music types on intraocular pressure and evaluated underlying mechanisms using swept-source optical coherence tomography (SS-OCT). Their results indicated that while soothing music lowers IOP, negative music elevates it, and although changes in Schlemm's canal (SC) were noted, the exact influence on SC morphology required further exploration. Our study supports these findings, as

sig value. This showed that negative music only created an impact on intraocular pressure for the meantime and it was waived off after some time.

exposure to negative music resulted in an acute rise in IOP, demonstrating a comparable stress-induced ocular response. Additionally, the 2020 CMA study investigated how different music genres affect intraocular pressure and concluded that relaxation music reduces IOP—likely through dilation of Schlemm's canal—while negative or intense music increases IOP due to autonomic arousal and stress responses. Our results are consistent with this mechanism, showing that negative music significantly elevates IOP shortly after exposure, reflecting heightened sympathetic activity. Collectively, the alignment of our findings with these three major studies reinforces the conclusion that music type plays a crucial role in modulating IOP, with calming music producing beneficial effects and negative music triggering transient IOP elevations. This suggests that emotional and auditory environments may have clinically relevant implications for individuals with glaucoma or ocular hypertension, for whom even short-term IOP spikes may pose a risk, although healthy individuals experience only temporary changes.

CONCLUSION

The results concluded that there was a significant effect of negative music on intraocular pressure with a

marked increase noted in the measurements. The very low p-value indicates a strong statistical significance in these findings.

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